

Studies on Reactivity of Molybdenyl(V) Cation in the Environment of Diverse Anions in Presence of 5-Nitro 1,10-Phenanthroline as an Organic Base

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New salts of oxohalomolybdate(V) ions, 5-nitro 1,10-phenanthroline oxopentachloro- and pentabromo molybdates, (5-nitrophenH₂) [MoOX₅] (X=Cl, Br), have been isolated in pure form for the first time. Reactions of these salts both in solution and in solid state lead to the synthesis of nonelectrolytic *cis*-[MoOX₅, 5-nitrophen], oxalato derivative [MoO.OX.Cl,5-nitrophen] and hydrolytic products [Mo₂O₄X₂(5-nitrophen)₂]. These compounds have been characterised by analytical and other physico-chemical techniques.

DEFINITE involvement of quinquevalent molybdenum in various biometabolisms has undoubtedly been confirmed by several authors^{1,2} for a long time. The chemistry of quinquevalent molybdenum is largely dominated by the oxomolybdenum "MoO⁵⁺" species which undergoes various chemical changes in different anionic environments³⁻⁵ at different conditions.

The present communication deals with the systematic study of the reactions of the molybdenyl cation MoO⁵⁺ in both halide and oxalate anionic environments in solutions and also in solid state, in presence of the ligand having [-N-C-C-N-] kind of linkage which has been demonstrated by the isolation of the salts of the type LH₂[MoOX₅], nonelectrolytes MoOX₅.L, oxalato derivative of the nonelectrolytic [MoO(OX)Cl.L] etc. (where L=5-nitro 1,10-phenanthroline and X=Cl, Br) for the first time. Close examination of the chemistry of pentavalent molybdenum clearly reveals that the characteristic chemical behaviour of the compounds largely depends on the basic nature of the organic ligands associated with them. The authors were, therefore, interested in exploring the differential activities of these quinquevalent molybdenum compounds particularly in presence of the substituted 1,10-phenanthroline e.g., 5-nitro 1,10 phenanthroline. It is interesting to note in this connection that the presence of a nitro group at the 5-position of the 1,10-phenanthroline in the ligand does not considerably affect the pronounced potentiality of the heterocyclic nitrogens. This is probably due to the fact that electron withdrawing nitro group is far apart from the basic nitrogen atoms.

The stereochemical constructions of the nonelectrolytes have been established by the present authors through the isolation and study of the hydrolytic products [Mo₂O₄.X₂.L₂]. Thermogravimetric investigations of the salts clearly

indicate the course through which the dehydrohalogenation and other transformations have taken place in solid state.

The compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis and other physico-chemical investigations.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A.R. grade. Molybdenum and halogens³⁻⁴ were estimated gravimetrically as MoO₃, AgCl and AgBr, respectively. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas' method. Oxalate was estimated by the standard KMnO₄ method applied to other similar⁶ oxalato complexes. Oxidation state of the metal was determined by ceric sulphate method.

Preparation :

1. 5-Nitro 1,10-phenanthroline oxopentachloromolybdate(V), 5-nitrophenH₂[MoOCl₅] : About 1.0 g of molybdenum trioxide was dissolved in 10 ml hot conc. hydrochloric acid with stirring followed by addition of 1 ml hydroiodic acid. The solution was boiled to drive off the liberated iodine. The concentrated small mass was taken up with minimum quantity of conc. hydrochloric acid when a bright green solution was obtained. To this solution, containing [MoOCl₅]²⁻, was added with stirring a solution of 1.56 g of 5-nitro 1,10 phenanthroline in minimum quantity of conc. hydrochloric acid. The mixture was cooled in ice when a yellowish green precipitate was obtained. The product was filtered and dried to constant weight in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH. Yield, about 2.5 g. Found : Mo, 18.92 ; Cl, 33.90 ; N, 7.8. Calcd. for C₁₂H₉N₂O₅MoOCl₅ i.e., 5-nitrophenH₂[MoOCl₅] ; Mo, 18.57 ; Cl, 34.42 ; N, 8.1%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 5.16.

2. *Oxotrichloro (5-nitro 1,10-phenanthroline) molybdenum(V)*, $[\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$: 1.0 g of the salt 5-nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOCl}_3]$ was refluxed with 10 ml of dehydrated ethanol for 1 hr. The mixture was cooled when a shining chocolate colour crystalline product precipitated. This was filtered, washed with minimum quantity of dehydrated ethanol and dried in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH to constant weight. Yield, about 0.72 g. Found: Mo, 21.72; Cl, 23.57; N, 9.1. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{MoOCl}_3$ i.e., $[\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$; Mo, 21.64; Cl, 24.01; N, 9.47%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 5.12.

This compound can also be prepared by dehydrohalogenation of the salt 5-nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOCl}_3]$ by heating at 130° in a tube furnace in a current of dry CO_2 .

3. *Oxo- μ -dioxochloro(5-nitro 1,10-phenanthroline) molybdenum(V)*, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(5\text{-nitrophen})_2]$: About 1.0 g of 5-nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOCl}_3]$ was gently boiled with 10 ml of 1:2 ethanol-water mixture for 15 min. The orange solid compound so precipitated was filtered and washed twice with cold water. It was dried in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH. Yield, about 0.7 g. Found: Mo, 24.58; Cl, 9.63; N, 10.55. Calcd. for $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(5\text{-nitrophen})_2]$; Mo, 24.7; Cl, 9.13; N, 10.81%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 4.86.

This compound can also be prepared from the non-electrolyte $[\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$ by hydrolysis. This reaction suggests the probable *cis*-configuration of $[\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$ as hydrolysis is followed by *trans*-elimination reaction.

4. *Oxochloro oxalato(5-nitro 1,10-phenanthroline) molybdenum(V)*, $[\text{MoO}(\text{OX})\text{Cl} \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$: About 0.562 g of freshly prepared $[\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$ was mixed with powdered oxalic acid in the 1:1 mole ratio and the resulting mixture was heated at an optimum temperature of 130° in a tube furnace in an atmosphere of dry CO_2 till the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased. The grey coloured product was washed with minimum quantity of dehydrated ethanol until free from unreacted oxalic acid and dried in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH. Yield, about 0.4 g. Found: Mo, 20.82; Cl, 7.73; $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, 19.74; N, 9.1. Calcd. for $[\text{MoO}(\text{OX}) \cdot \text{Cl} \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$; Mo, 20.84; Cl, 7.70; $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, 19.1; N, 9.12%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 4.96.

An attempt was made to hydrolyse this oxalato derivative but no pure compound could be isolated.

5. *5-Nitro 1,10-phenanthroline oxopentabromomolybdate(V)*, 5-nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$: About 1.0 g of molybdenum trioxide was gently reduced with 10 ml 48% boiling hydrobromic acid and was evaporated almost to dryness. The residual mass was taken up with 10 ml 48% hydrobromic acid and the operation repeated twice. Finally, the residue was dissolved in 10 ml of the same boiling acid and 1.56 g of 5-nitro 1,10-phenanthroline, dissolved in minimum quantity of the same acid was added to

this with stirring. The mixture on cooling to room temperature yielded a yellow crystalline solid compound. The product was filtered, washed with hydrobromic acid and dried in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH to constant weight. Yield, about 4.6 g. Found: Mo, 12.98; Br, 54.16; N, 5.5. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{MoOBr}_5$ i.e., 5-nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$; Mo, 12.99; Br, 54.12; N, 5.68%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 4.88.

6. *Oxotribromo(5-nitro 1,10-phenanthroline) molybdenum(V)*, $[\text{MoOBr}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$: About 1.0 g of 5-nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOBr}_3]$ was heated in a tube furnace at 150° in an atmosphere of dry CO_2 till the evolution of hydrogen bromide ceased. The orange red product was washed with minimum quantity of dehydrated ethanol and dried in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH to constant weight. Yield, about 0.5 g. Found: Mo, 16.22; Br, 42.48; N, 7.05. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{MoOBr}_3$ i.e., $[\text{MoOBr}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$; Mo, 16.63; Br, 41.59; N, 7.27%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 5.11.

The attempted dehydrohalogenation of the salt 5-nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOBr}_3]$ in dehydrated ethanolic solution failed due to the formation of impure products.

7. *Oxo- μ -dioxobromo(5-nitro 1,10-phenanthroline) molybdenum(V)*, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2(5\text{-nitrophen})_2]$: About 1.2 g of 5-nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOBr}_3]$ was treated with 10 ml of 1:2 ethanol water mixture and boiled for 15 min. A brown solid precipitated on cooling to room temperature. The product was washed twice with cold water and dried in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH to constant weight. Yield, about 0.5 g. Found: Mo, 21.49; Br, 19.10; N, 9.50%. Calcd. for $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2(5\text{-nitrophen})_2]$; Mo, 22.17; Br, 18.45; N, 9.69%.

This compound can also be prepared by the hydrolysis of the non-electrolyte $[\text{MoOBr}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$ by ethanol-water mixture. By this reaction the *cis*-configuration of the non-electrolyte has been established as hydrolysis proceeds through *trans*-elimination reaction.

Conductance measurements: Molar conductances at different dilutions were measured in aqueous medium in a "dip type" cell for the salts 5-nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOX}_3]$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$). The results showed that the salts were extensively hydrolysed in aqueous solution. Conductances of $[\text{MoOX}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$ and $[\text{MoO}(\text{OX})\text{Cl} \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$ were measured in nitrobenzene solution. These are 3.01, 1.63 and 3.63 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$ for chloro, bromo and oxalato derivatives, respectively. These values are much less than those for binary electrolytes⁷ indicating non-electrolytic nature of the compounds in conformity with their molecular formula. No suitable solvents, however, could be found for $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{X}_2(5\text{-nitrophen})_2]$.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements: Magnetic susceptibilities of the compounds were measured

in Gouy balance using a field strength of 8500 gauss. The values of the μ_{eff} are 1.67(300), 1.43(300), 0.706(295), 1.88(300), 1.72(300), 1.71(303) and 0.69(297) B.M. for 5-nitrophen $H_2[MoOCl_5]$, $[MoOCl_5 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$, $[Mo_2O_4Cl_2 \cdot (5\text{-nitrophen})_2]$, $[MoO(OX)Cl \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$, 5-nitrophen $H_2[MoOBr_5]$, $[MoOBr_5 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$ and $[Mo_2O_4Br_2 \cdot (5\text{-nitrophen})_2]$, respectively. (Figures in the parentheses are the temperatures in the absolute scale). Values

of μ_{eff} are calculated as $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.839 (\chi'_M \cdot T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ B.M., where χ'_M = corrected molar susceptibility $\chi_M + \chi_d$ (χ_M being the uncorrected value and χ_d the diamagnetic correction for ligands). The values are in fair agreement with the d^1 configuration of the trivalent molybdenum. The hydrolytic product $[Mo_2O_4X_2 \cdot (5\text{-nitrophen})_2]$ has small values of magnetic moment due to oxobridges⁸ with the possible Mo-Mo interaction.

Thermogravimetric analysis : Thermogravimetric investigations were carried out in MOM derivatograph, Hungary, for recording DTA, the rate of heating being 10°/min. The thermo-couple was Pt-Pt-Rh. The reference inert sample was $\alpha-Al_2O_3$. The results of the thermogravimetric analysis of the salts $LH_2[MoOX_5]$ ($X = Cl, Br$ and $L = 5\text{-nitrophen}$) are plotted in Figs. 1 and 2. Investigations were made under the influence of dynamic dry air. It is evident from the curves that the chloro salt $LH_2[MoOCl_5]$ undergoes loss of weight near 130° and becomes stable to the nonelectrolytic form $[LMOCl_5]$ with the elimination of two molecules of hydrogen chloride at 160° as supported by the strong endothermic peak of the DTA curve. Dehydrohalogenation takes place with 13.6% loss of weight against the theoretically estimated value of 14.1%. The slight deviation may be due to the presence of moisture in the sample.

The second medium sharp endothermic change occurs at 260° indicating the formation of the stable oxidised form LMO_5 with the observed 30.9% weight loss against the anticipated value of 29.0%. The discrepancy between these values suggests that the decomposition is incomplete at this temperature and an intermediate compound must be formed. Finally, the formation of the most stable final product MoO_3 with the elimination of one molecule of ligand per molecule of LMO_5 has been indicated with the 72.9% loss of weight in comparison to the theoretical loss of 72.1%. The compound starts loss of weight around 550° and becomes stable at 650°. This is also supported by the DTA curve. The successive changes may be represented schematically as follows :

Fig. 1. T. G. and D. T. A. curves for 5-nitrophen $H_2[MoOCl_5]$.

Fig. 2. T. G. and D. T. A. curves for 5-nitrophen $H_2[MoOBr_5]$.

In contrast to the chloro salt, the bromo salt $LH_2[MoOBr_5]$ starts loss of weight near 100° and becomes stable to the nonelectrolytic form,

L MoOBr_3 , with the elimination of two molecules of hydrogen bromide per molecule of the compound at 170°, as is evident from the strong and sharp endothermic peak in the DTA curve. The dehydrohalogenation takes place with 22.9% loss of weight in comparison to the anticipated value of 22.0%. The small deviation may be due to the adhered moisture of the sample.

The second broad and medium endothermic band appears at 308° in the DTA curve indicating the formation of the intermediate L MoO_2Br , with the observed 40.2% loss of weight against the theoretical value of 41.4%. The third endothermic change probably occurs at 510° as is evident from the DTA curve. The formation of the oxidised form, L MoO_3 , may be suggested with the 48% observed loss of weight against the theoretical value of 50%. Finally, the most stable state, MoO_3 , is attained at 620° with the elimination of one molecule of ligand per molecule of the parent L MoO_3 . The compound starts loss of weight at 550° and becomes constant at 620° as indicated by the TG diagram. The formation of the stable oxide has been verified as the observed loss is about 79% in comparison with the theoretical loss of 80.5%. So the process of oxidation of the bromo-salt, which proceeds via the formation of the nonelectrolyte, involves the following suggested steps :

Infrared spectra : IR spectra of the compounds were recorded in Perkin-Elmer IR spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. The main bands are given in Table 1. IR spectra of the compounds show strong absorption bands in the region 930-980 cm^{-1} due to the Mo(V)=O stretching vibration^{3,4}. The metal-oxygen chain ($-\text{Mo-O-Mo-O}$) vibration may be located in the broad bands in the region 700-800 cm^{-1} in the hydrolytic products $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{X}_2 \cdot (5\text{-nitrophen})_2$. IR bands of the non-electrolytic oxalato derivative $[\text{MoO}(\text{OX})\text{Cl} \cdot (5\text{-nitrophen})]$ around 1630 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ stretching, 1330 cm^{-1} to the $\nu_{\text{C-O}} + \nu_{\text{C-C}}$ stretching and 910 cm^{-1} and 1200 cm^{-1} to the $\nu_{\text{C-O}} + \delta_{\text{O-C-O}}$ stretching. The assignments on the oxalato derivative were made on the basis of the previous⁶ work on oxalato complexes.

Electronic spectra : The solution spectra of the compounds were recorded in Varian Series 634 UV spectrophotometer using AnalaR grade solvents. Hydrochloric acid, 12 M, was used as a solvent for 5-nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOCl}_3]$ and AnalaR grade acetonitrile for the non-electrolytic complex $[\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$ including oxalato derivative. The solvent used in the case of 5-nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOBr}_3]$ was

TABLE 1—INFRARED BANDS IN cm^{-1}

Compound	Main bands
5-nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOCl}_3]$	600w, 700m, 715m, 810vs, 895s, 980vs, 1330s, 1355vs, 1415w, 1450w, 1540vs, 1620sb, 1680w, 3070w, 3270wb.
$[\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$	650vw, 720s, 760w, 820s, 840s, 900m, 940w, 970vs, 1150m, 1330vs, 1420s, 1520vs.
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2 \cdot (5\text{-nitrophen})_2]$	710m, 800w, 825m, 940vs, 1140w, 1320s, 1420m, 1510vs.
$[\text{MoO}(\text{OX})\text{Cl} \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$	660w, 720s, 740w, 760m, 825s, 840s, 910mb, 940w, 970vs, 1120w, 1150m, 1200w, 1330vs, 1420s, 1630w, 1750mb.
5-Nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOBr}_3]$	690m, 710w, 800s, 880m, 980s, 1090w, 1140w, 1310s, 1350vs, 1440w, 1520sh, 1600sb, 3060sb.
$[\text{MoOBr}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$	715s, 730vw, 745w, 770wb, 830s, 900w, 965vs, 1145m, 1330sb, 1420m, 1500m.
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2 \cdot (5\text{-nitrophen})_2]$	660w, 730sb, 760m.sh, 820m.sh, 840s, 910s, 960vs, 1120vw, 1160m, 1190w, 1210w, 1340vs, 1400w, 1430s, 1520vs, 1590w, 1640w, 3060wb, 3400wb.

w=weak ; m=medium ; s=strong ; vs=very strong ; vw=very weak ; sh=shoulder ; wb=weak broad.

TABLE 2

Compound	λ_{max} in $\text{m}\mu$	ν ($\text{cm}^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$)	Molar extinction coefficient	Assignment
5-Nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOCl}_3]$	700	14.3	34	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E}(\text{I})$
	430	23.3	48	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1$
	310	32.3	20,3000	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E}(\text{II})$
	281	35.6	39,0600	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1(\text{I})$
$[\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$	239	41.8	33,7000	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E}(\text{III})$
	700	14.3	192	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E}(\text{I})$
	529	19.0	422	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1$
	322	31.10	7460	L \rightarrow Mo
$[\text{MoO}(\text{OX})\text{Cl} \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$	265	37.70	18,300	Charge transfer
	225	44.40	22,100	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1(\text{I})$
	531	18.9	274	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1(\text{II})$
	319	31.4	5360	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E}(\text{I})$
	264	37.8	12,910	L \rightarrow Mo
5-Nitrophen $\text{H}_2[\text{MoOBr}_3]$	227	44.0	15,390	Charge transfer
	670	14.9	240	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1(\text{I})$
	471	21.3	5420	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E}(\text{I})$
	414	24.1	31,120	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1(\text{II})$
	370	27.0	29,800	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1(\text{I})$
	280	35.7	229,000	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E}(\text{II})$
$[\text{MoOBr}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$	247	40.4	225,800	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E}(\text{III})$
	747	13.38	180	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E}(\text{I})$
	542	18.44	1,158	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1$
	476	21.05	992	L \rightarrow Mo
	395	25.31	3,262	Charge transfer
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2 \cdot (5\text{-nitrophen})_2]$	264	37.87	22,520	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1(\text{I})$
	224	44.65	28,920	$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1(\text{II})$
				$^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E}(\text{III})$

48% HBr and AnalaR grade acetonitrile for the non-electrolytic complex $[\text{MoOBr}_3 \cdot 5\text{-nitrophen}]$. No suitable solvent could be found for the binuclear complexes $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2 \cdot (5\text{-nitrophen})_2]$ and $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2 \cdot (5\text{-nitrophen})_2]$ and their reflectance spectra were taken in solid state using paraffin base.

The assignments made on the basis of observation in identical cases⁹⁻¹¹ are tabulated in Table 2 and 3.

TABLE 3—REFLECTANCE SPECTRA IN SOLID STATE

Compounds	ν ($\text{cm}^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$)	Inten- sities	Assignment
[Mo ₂ O ₄ Cl ₂ .(5-nitrophen) ₂]	13.7	w	² B ₂ → ² E(I)
	17.5	m, sh	² B ₂ → ² B ₁
	23.0	s	L → Mo
[Mo ₂ O ₄ Br ₂ .(5-nitrophen) ₂]	25.4	vs	Charge transfer
	13.8	w	² B ₂ → ² B ₂ (I)
	16.6	m, sh	² B ₂ → ² E(I)
	22.9	s	² B ₂ → ² B ₁
	25.0	vs, b	L → Mo Charge transfer ² B ₂ → ² B ₂ (I)

m=medium ; sh=shoulder ; w=weak ; s=strong ; b=broad ; vs=very strong.

Results and Discussion

The basicity of the substituted 1,10-phenanthroline i.e., 5-nitrophen is such that the dehydrohalogenation of the salts 5-nitrophen[MoOX₃] either in solvent or in solid state would be controlled only to the resultant stereospecific *cis*-nonelectrolytic [MoOX₃.5-nitrophen] products. The configuration of the non-electrolytes were determined from their mode of hydrolysis through the most expected *trans*-elimination reactions leading to the isolation of the dioxobridged compounds [Mo₂O₄X₂-(5-nitrophen)₂].

The presence of the oxobridges in the hydrolytic products were confirmed from their low magnetic moment values. In contrast to the identical cases^{3,4} of MoOX₃.phen, all the attempts of

isolating the MoOX₃.5-nitrophen in another stereochemical form failed.

The molybdenum oxygen bonding interactions have been treated for the ion [MoOCl₅]²⁻ on the basis of a tetragonal structure with a short Mo-O bond⁹. The observed electronic spectra of the compounds containing the [MoOX₃]²⁻ ionic species taken in hydrogen halide acid medium are in good agreement with the spectra of the (NH₄)₂[MoOCl₅] taken in 12 M HCl. It would therefore be reasonable to conclude that the salts so isolated evidently contain the oxopentahalo molybdate ion.

The presence of the d¹ electron in these compounds is evident from the magnetic data.

In explaining the spectra of the low symmetry non-electrolytic complexes, electronic transitions were reconciled with the standard assignments for previously synthesised similar compounds^{1,2}.

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